

Assessment of Reading Habits and English Writing Skills of Grade 11 Senior High School Students of Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos Incorporated

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Date Submitted:
March 11, 2026

Date Accepted:
April 25, 2026

Date Published:
May 22, 2026

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.20329757

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the reading habits and English writing skills of Grade 11 Senior High School students of Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos Incorporated. Specifically, it aimed to determine the students' frequency of reading, types of materials read, and level of writing proficiency in terms of grammar, coherence, vocabulary, and organization. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, utilizing a validated questionnaire and writing assessment tool administered to selected respondents. Data were analyzed using mean scores and correlation analysis. Findings revealed that students demonstrated moderate reading habits, with increased reading engagement primarily during academic requirements such as examinations. In terms of writing skills, students exhibited an average level of proficiency, with

difficulties noted in grammar and idea organization. Results further indicated a significant relationship between reading habits and writing performance. Aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Sustainable Development Goal 4, this study highlights the importance of strengthening literacy skills as a foundation for inclusive and equitable quality education. It recommends the implementation of reading enhancement programs and targeted writing interventions to support students' academic development and lifelong learning.

Keywords: *Reading habits, English writing skills, San Carlos City, Philippines, Quantitative Descriptive-correlational.*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a vital ability that students develop when studying English. Reading and writing hold great importance that goes beyond just grades; they are essential skills that shape how students communicate, think critically, and develop their minds (Graham, 2020). Additionally, Pramita and Atmazaki (2021) reported that a student's reading habit might help them arrange the material they read. Different types of reading might have varying effects on writing abilities. Students can develop their writing abilities in a more structured and formal manner by reading academic materials such as textbooks and scholarly papers. Literary reading, in contrast, can nurture creativity and storytelling abilities, giving students the chance to explore various voices and styles in their writing (Suseno & Wijaya, 2021).

Reading habits are a significant factor in a student's overall academic success. Among the essential skills that English language learners need to develop, reading holds significant importance. Magasvaran et.al.(2022) emphasized that reading serves as a foundation for other language skills, enabling students to become better writers and speakers. This emphasizes how crucial it is to develop these behaviors in order to guarantee that students are prepared to meet the demands of their coursework.

Additionally, one essential talent for success in school and the workplace is the ability to write well in English. Extensive reading has been shown in numerous studies to significantly enhance writing abilities. Interacting with different types of texts helps students discover a range of vocabulary, sentence styles, and writing norms, which they can weave into their own writing. Research shows that students who read often are likely to create more coherent and grammatically correct written pieces (Jannah et al., 2021). Consequently, a significant obstacle that students face when writing is the absence of logical concept sequencing and coherence. A common issue with university students' writing, according to Inayatullah and Abidin (2021), is the lack of a clear structure and flow, which makes the text hard for the reader to understand. This highlights that writing is a systematic process that calls on students to make logical connections between their ideas from one paragraph to the next, in addition to being a creative one.

In the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), 15-year-old Filipino students ranked last in reading proficiency among all countries/territories, with only 19% meeting the minimum (Level 2) standard. Given that English is one of our official languages, the Philippines have one of the highest percentages of English-speaking populations in the world—66% of the population speaks the language fluently. According to a local survey conducted in 2023 by Social Weather Stations, 55% of Filipinos can speak and write English, while 69% of them can write it. Just over 9% of people do not use any of these abilities.

This study is to give a descriptive evaluation of Grade 11 senior high school students' reading habits and English writing abilities. In addition to providing insight into the current status of these factors, the study's findings can guide administrators and teachers in developing targeted strategies to improve students' reading habits and English writing skills. In the end, the findings of this study will support further initiatives to raise Grade 11 Senior High School students' English language competency.

Research Questions

This study aims to assess the reading habits and English writing skills of Grade 11 senior high school students of Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos Incorporated. Specifically, it seeks to provide answers to the following:

1. What are the reading habits of the grade 11 Senior High School students in terms of:
 - a. Frequency of reading
 - b. Types of reading materials
 - c. Time spent on reading
2. What is the level of English writing skills of the grade 11 Senior High School in terms of:
 - a. Grammar
 - b. Vocabulary
 - c. Sentence structure
3. What is the significant relationship between the reading habits and the English writing skills of the Grade 11 senior high school students?
4. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention programs or recommendations may be proposed to enhance students' reading habits and improve their English writing skills?

Literature Review

Reading habits

Reading remains a vital academic skill, yet it faces growing challenges in today's digital era. The rise of social media and online entertainment has contributed to a decline in students' reading frequency and engagement. Many learners now prefer accessible, fast-paced digital content over traditional printed materials, affecting their motivation and overall reading behaviour. These shifts place added pressure on educators, who must navigate outdated strategies, limited resources, and increasing classroom distractions. Despite these obstacles, students continue to adopt adaptive strategies such as using digital tools, setting reading routines, and seeking conducive reading environments. These patterns highlight the need for supportive interventions and innovative approaches to strengthen sustained reading habits among senior high school students.

Setiani, et al (2025) found that students with higher frequency of reading tend to develop more effective reading strategies, positively affecting comprehension outcomes. It also aligns with the broader body of literature suggesting that frequent reading fosters vocabulary expansion and background knowledge, an idea reflected in Stanovich's Matthew Effect theory, which posits that the more one reads, the richer one's linguistic and cognitive resources become, thereby enhancing comprehension. It shows that readers who engage regularly with diverse texts are better able to make inferences and understand complex ideas. Additionally, frequent reading exposes students to a wide range of sentence structures and writing styles, which contributes to their overall linguistic fluency. This cumulative effect creates a cycle of improvement, where enhanced reading skills lead to greater reading engagement, further reinforcing cognitive development.

Subsequently, Gandari and Jaya (2025) observe that students' reading habits are significantly influenced by the types of reading materials they encounter. Most students reported a strong preference for printed reading materials such as textbooks and physical books, arguing that print helps them focus better and avoid distractions that often come with digital devices. However, a number of students also favored digital reading formats, including e-books and online texts, for their convenience, portability, and the broader variety of content available—especially in genres like fiction (e.g., novels) and non-fiction (e.g., biographies). Furthermore, when given the option, a majority of students preferred a combination of both printed and digital materials, as this mix was reported to make reading more varied and engaging, which in turn positively affected their reading motivation and habits.

The study on Indonesian EFL learners' digital reading habits (Pardede et al, 2023) reveals that students dedicate a substantial amount of time to reading both for academic and non-academic purposes, with participants spending on average 2.6 hours per day (12.8 hours per week) on academic reading and 1.9 hours per day (9.7 hours per week) on non-academic reading. These findings suggest that the amount of time students allocate to reading extends beyond classroom requirements and reflects broader engagement with texts in their daily routines. The relatively high time investment for non-academic reading, which exceeds similar measures reported in prior international studies, indicates that students' habits include voluntary reading activities in addition to obligatory academic tasks. This consistent and considerable time commitment is closely tied to the development and reinforcement of reading habits, as students who read more frequently tend to strengthen their reading routines. Additionally, both academic and non-academic reading contribute to cognitive and linguistic gains, further encouraging students to sustain their reading habits over time.

According to Wani & Ismael (2024), reading, which is a vital skill crucial for comprehension and academic success, faces challenges in the modern era marked by the digital age and prevalent social media. This has significantly marked an era where the frequency of reading, especially among younger generations, has been declining. In the academe, challenges in teaching reading arise from instructional strategies, the selection of materials, and the use of ineffective pedagogical approaches. Distractions introduced by the digital shift, particularly through social media and online entertainment, pose difficulties in maintaining students' engagement with reading.

One major factor on this issue is the immense amount of time people spend on social media. This is in line with the findings of Samsuddin & Aspura (2021), who showed that most respondents would rather spend their free time on social media platforms than reading. This finding has greatly put the biggest problem at stake: when people, particularly students, tend to expend their free time on social media rather than reading, this would, most likely,

affect their academic performance. To overcome these obstacles, which are highly challenging on the part of the educators, they must stay committed to be able to develop a resolution on this emerging pitfall in the academe.

Hassan et al (2021) argued that reading habits significantly influence various aspects of reading behaviour, including material selection, engagement in reading activities, time allocation for reading, choice of reading locations, and levels of reader motivation. This places the academe at a damning disadvantage, that students will most likely prefer to spend their time reading short-time, fast-paced, digitally published materials rather than the traditional ones, that most likely, are still used by most schools as resources. This is in line with the findings by Baba and Affendi (2020), who found out that most respondents (67.5%) leaned towards digital materials, while the remaining 32.5% indicated a preference for printed texts. Individuals have the ability to conveniently access electronic books at no cost or opt for paid online services.

This is most likely because digital materials and resources are convenient, cost efficient, and reusable. At this point, the steps toward battling this dilemma becomes clearer, this calls for innovation. According to Nite (2025) despite these challenges, learners employed various strategies to overcome barriers, such as using digital tools like Google and online dictionaries, establishing reading routines, choosing quiet reading environments, and leveraging context clues to aid comprehension. These adaptive approaches underscore the importance of supportive interventions, such as access to engaging reading materials, time management guidance, and structured reading programs, to foster a culture of meaningful and sustained reading among senior high school students.

Reading, a fundamental skill for comprehension and academic growth, is increasingly challenged by the dominance of digital technology and social media. Students now spend more of their free time on online platforms rather than reading, which affects their academic performance and weakens traditional reading habits. As digital materials become more accessible, affordable, and convenient, learners tend to prefer quick, fast-paced online content over printed texts, making it harder for educators to sustain engagement through conventional methods. Despite these challenges, many students adopt strategies such as using digital tools, establishing reading routines, and seeking quiet environments to support their understanding. These patterns highlight the need for innovative and supportive interventions that encourage meaningful and sustained reading among senior high school learners.

English Writing Skills

Writing is essential for English language learners, requiring skills in organization, coherence, grammar, and vocabulary. Learning this is hard but to teach and evaluate written outputs are much harder than we perceive it to be. Teaching writing in English presents a range of persistent challenges for educators, particularly when students struggle with grammar, vocabulary, idea development, and motivation. Despite the importance of writing in academic settings, this skill often receives limited instructional time and insufficiently varied teaching approaches. These difficulties have become even more pronounced with the growing dependence of students on artificial intelligence tools for generating written work. As technology advances rapidly, educators face the troubling reality of increasingly inauthentic student submissions produced by AI systems. While these tools offer certain benefits for improving writing performance, they also create concerns regarding plagiarism, overreliance, and the accuracy of generated information. Consequently, schools are now compelled to strengthen students' digital literacy to ensure responsible and informed use of artificial intelligence in academic writing.

Recent study by Irmawati et. Al (2024) demonstrates a positive, moderate correlation between students' grammar mastery and their writing skills, indicating that grammatical knowledge plays an important role in effective writing. This relationship suggests that a solid understanding of grammar, particularly tense usage, supports students in producing clearer and more accurate written texts. However, writing proficiency is not determined by grammar alone, as vocabulary mastery, content development, organization, and writing conventions also contribute significantly to writing quality. Therefore, grammar functions as a foundational component that works in conjunction with other linguistic and cognitive skills to enhance overall writing performance. By integrating grammar instruction with vocabulary development, practice, and feedback, teaching and learning processes can more effectively support students in developing strong and well-rounded writing abilities.

The reviewed studies by Raju et.al (2024) highlights a strong and consistent connection between vocabulary knowledge and writing skills, emphasizing that effective writing depends not only on knowing many words but also on understanding them deeply. Vocabulary depth enables learners to select precise and contextually appropriate words, which supports clearer idea development and more fluent written expression. In addition, productive vocabulary plays a critical role in writing performance, as it allows students to actively use their lexical knowledge to convey meaning in written form. Students with sufficient vocabulary tend to perceive writing as easier and more manageable, while those with limited vocabulary often struggle to express their ideas effectively. These findings suggest that vocabulary knowledge functions as a key predictor of writing proficiency, influencing both the quality and ease of writing. Integrating vocabulary development strategies into writing instruction can significantly support students in achieving higher levels of writing performance.

When writing in a foreign language, it is important for students to understand and review the correct sentence structure. According to Imaniah (2022), many students tend to translate directly from their mother tongue, which can result in sentences that are difficult to understand because the arrangement of elements differs between languages. In English, for example, subjects and verbs must coexist in a sentence to convey a clear meaning. Not all grammatical rules are universal, so mastering sentence structure requires careful study and practice. Indicators of sentence structure mastery include understanding sentence ambiguity, arranging sentence elements correctly, knowing different types of phrases, identifying phrases and clauses, recognizing overall sentence structure, comparing structures with other languages, and being able to produce complete sentences. Students need to focus on eliminating ambiguity, using proper conjunctions for cohesion, and distinguishing between phrases and clauses. By paying attention to these aspects, students can construct sentences that are both grammatically correct and logically organized. Mastery of sentence structure ultimately allows students to write clear, coherent, and well-organized texts that effectively communicate their ideas.

As stated by Amalia, et al. (2020) there are seven challenges faced by the teachers during teaching writing to students. Those challenges encompass (1) students' poor English grammatical competence, 2) students' incapability of developing ideas for English writing, (3) students' inadequate English vocabulary knowledge, 4) students' demotivation to learn English writing, (5) insufficient time management to teach English writing, 6) limited sources of English writing materials, and (7) limited facilities to teach English writing. Although writing is an indispensable component of English courses, academic writing rarely receives sufficient attention. For example, writing instruction generally focuses on grammatical rules and accuracy in language use, with comparatively little attention given to process-oriented writing instruction. Consequently, the challenge heightened as more students rely on artificial intelligence tools as their resort– which puts the academe at a great disadvantage.

With the rapid development of technology in the world, the academe faces a reproachful truth: insincere written academic works because of the rise of artificial intelligences, including ChatGPT. Kohnke et al., (2023) defined ChatGPT as a generative AI- enabled chat bot that can generate outputs responding to varied and complex prompts (e.g., languages, instructions, questions) and engage in sustained human- like interactions. Scholars have reported on the pedagogical benefits of using ChatGPT for language teaching and learning, including acting as a conversation partner and reference tool. Because of this tool, more and more educators find it hard to evaluate their student's work. Due to the release of ChatGPT and other generative AI tools, there is a pressing need for school-age learners to develop digital competencies (Cervera & Caena, 2022).

ChatGPT has been recognized for its potential in enhancing writing performance (Huang and Tan, 2023). The AI-powered tool facilitates the production of coherent and cohesive text by providing learners with immediate feedback and alternative grammatically correct sentences (Huang and Tan, 2023). However, it is important to consider certain limitations when using ChatGPT for different writing tasks. Frequent reliance on generated text from ChatGPT may hinder language learners' own writing abilities. Additionally, using the generated text without appropriate review and editing may lead to issues of plagiarism that should be carefully addressed.

In certain situations, artificial intelligence tools cannot be fully trusted. Particularly, Javier & Moonhouse (2024) shared that when students attempted to ask questions as a traveler to the city their school was located in Brgy, Pinugay in Baras, the responses, while seeming to be authoritative and correct, were factually inaccurate. In

times like this, it is safe to assume that while artificial intelligence tools provide us with convenience, just like us, it has its limitations.

Writing remains one of the most challenging skills for English language learners, and teachers continue to struggle with issues such as weak grammar, limited vocabulary, difficulty generating ideas, and low motivation among students. These challenges are compounded by time constraints, limited instructional resources, and the growing dependence on artificial intelligence tools, which often leads to inauthentic or plagiarized written outputs. Although artificial intelligence tools like ChatGPT can enhance writing by offering feedback and language support, their misuse can hinder students' independent writing development and even produce inaccurate information. As a result, educators face increasing difficulty evaluating student work and must now prioritize digital literacy to ensure responsible and effective use of artificial intelligence in academic writing.

METHODS

Research Design

In this study, the descriptive-correlational quantitative research design was used. The study's main goal is to systematically evaluate and characterize the current state of the two primary research variables—the reading habits and English writing skills of the target population, specifically the grade 11 senior high school students at Colegio de Sta. Rita de San Carlos Inc. By collecting quantitative data to precisely show the current state and characteristics of the phenomenon being studied, the descriptive approach effectively answers the “what is” question without changing variables or establishing causal relationships. It is non-experimental. A thorough quantitative profile of the variables as they currently appear was provided by summarizing and analyzing the data using descriptive statistics.

Respondents of the Study

The participants were the Grade 11 Senior High School students of Colegio de Sta. Rita, San Carlos City, enrolled for the School Year 2025–2026. The Grade 11 population consists of 239 students, with 91 males (38%) and 148 females (62%). Using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator with a 5% margin of error, 95% confidence level, and 50% response distribution, the finite population adjusted sample size for 239 students is 148 respondents. To ensure equal representation in the study, 74 males and 74 females are selected through stratified random sampling. This sampling method prevents gender imbalance and supports a more accurate assessment of students' reading habits and English writing skills.

Research Instrument

In assessing the Reading Habits and English Writing Skills of Senior High School Students of Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos Incorporated, this uses two (2) sets of questionnaires. This study's main tool is a two-category survey questionnaire created by the researcher specially to gauge senior high school students' reading habits and English writing skills.

The first part of the questionnaire focused on three key indicators of reading habits, namely: frequency of reading, types of reading materials, and time spent reading. These indicators served as the basis for the construction of the questionnaire. Each indicator consisted of five (5) items, ensuring equal representation of each dimension. To ensure alignment with the objectives of the study, each indicator was translated into measurable variables and corresponding statements.

The response options for this part of the questionnaire followed a five-point Likert scale, ranging from Always (5), Often (4), Sometimes (3), Rarely (2), to Never (1). This scaling method allowed the respondents to indicate the extent to which each statement described their reading habits.

Data Collection Procedure

In order to gather the necessary data of the grade 11 senior high school students for the study on the assessment of reading habits and English writing skills of Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos Incorporated, the researchers asked permission from the school administrators and use the researcher-made survey questionnaires to administer a survey. The responders received a formal consent form explaining the study's goal and their involvement in it, along with a copy to the office of the school administration. To ensure anonymity and in accordance with the class schedule of the students, surveys were disseminated in soft copies via Google Forms. This ensured that the data collection will provide accessibility and comfort for both the researchers and the respondents.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the respondents were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to determine the reading habits and English writing skills of Grade 11 Senior High School students of Colegio de Sta. Rita de San Carlos Incorporated. The weighted mean and standard deviation were used to describe the respondents' reading habits in terms of frequency of reading, types of reading materials, and time spent reading, as well as to assess their level of English writing skills. The weighted mean determined the average responses of the participants, while the standard deviation measured the consistency and variability of their responses.

The responses in the questionnaire were interpreted using a five-point Likert scale with the following verbal interpretations: 4.21–5.00 as Always, 3.41–4.20 as Often, 2.61–3.40 as Sometimes, 1.81–2.60 as Rarely, and 1.00–1.80 as Never. Furthermore, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was employed to determine the significant relationship between reading habits and English writing skills of the respondents. The level of significance was set at 0.05 to determine whether the relationship between the variables was statistically significant. All data collected through Google Forms were organized, tabulated, interpreted, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher adheres to the ethical guidelines and address the general principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice to ensure the ethical soundness of the study. This study highlights the value of inclusion and guarantees that every student has an equal chance to advance their writing and reading abilities. The confidentiality of student data and academic records must be given top priority by researchers. This principle is also in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, where no information that discloses the assessor's identity shall be released or published unless deemed necessary without their consent to protect their rights and welfare. Participants' informed consent should be obtained by researchers, as well as parental or guardian consent in the case of children. To avoid the identity of specific students, data should be anonymized and stored in secure systems to protect the information gathered. To preserve privacy, data should only be accessible to authorized people, and findings should only be shared in aggregate form.

Before consenting to participate, students and, if relevant, their parents or guardians, must be thoroughly informed about the nature, goal, and possible significance of the research. There must be no undue influence or compulsion, and participation must be completely voluntary. Reminding participants that they can leave the research at any moment without facing any repercussions is important. The goal, methods, possible hazards, and advantages of the research must all be well understood by participants, as well as by their parents or legal guardians in the case of children. Everything that has to be known is included in a comprehensive permission form that can be distributed easily and clearly.

Throughout the study process, researchers must treat every participant with respect and decency. Assuring their engagement is voluntary, appreciating and respecting their viewpoints, and protecting their privacy and confidentiality are all necessary to achieve this. Researchers should avoid interfering with students' academic routines by being considerate of their time and dedication to their studies. Participants should also be given the chance to voice any concerns or ask questions at any time, as well as be informed on the study's results. Above all, we, the researchers will ensure that dedication and truthfulness will be practiced as the study proceeds.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reading Habits

Table 4A. Survey results on the Reading habits of the respondents in terms of Frequency of Reading

STATEMENT	5		4		3		2		1		TOTAL	SD	WX	I	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%					
Frequency of Reading															
I read academic materials regularly for my class requirements.	18	12.16%	49	33.11%	68	45.95%	9	6.08%	4	2.70	148	100%	0.61	3.45	S
I read non-academic materials (stories, blogs, articles, etc.) on my own.	25	16.89%	43	29.05%	70	47.30%	9	6.08%	1	0.68	148	100%	0.63	3.55	S
I read even when there are no school tasks requiring it.	16	10.81%	43	29.05%	72	48.65%	13	8.78%	4	2.70	148	100%	0.59	3.36	S
I make reading part of my daily routine.	19	12.84%	46	31.08%	68	45.95%	13	8.78%	2	1.35	148	100%	0.61	3.45	S
I choose reading over other leisure activities (e.g., scrolling, gaming, etc.).	8	5.41%	41	27.70%	79	53.38%	19	12.84%	1	0.68	148	100%	0.56	3.24	S

Frequency of Reading

The data indicate that students demonstrate a moderate level of reading frequency, with all responses falling under the “Sometimes” category. Reading academic materials for class requirements obtained a weighted mean of 3.45, interpreted as Sometimes, suggesting that while students engage with required readings, this is not done consistently at a high frequency.

Similarly, making reading part of their daily routine also garnered a weighted mean of 3.45, indicating that although students attempt to integrate reading into their everyday activities, it is not yet firmly established as a consistent habit. Reading when there are no school tasks requiring it yielded a slightly lower mean of 3.36, which reflects a limited tendency to read beyond academic obligations.

Among all indicators, reading non-academic materials on their own recorded the highest weighted mean of 3.55, still interpreted as Sometimes. This suggests that students are more inclined toward voluntary or interest-based reading compared to structured academic tasks.

In contrast, reading for leisure activities (e.g., scrolling, gaming-related content) registered the lowest weighted mean of 3.24, although it remains within the Sometimes range. This indicates that reading is not the primary form of leisure among students, who may prefer other forms of entertainment during their free time.

Overall, while reading is present across different contexts—academic, routine, and personal—it remains at a moderate level, with a noticeable preference for non-academic reading and less engagement in reading as a leisure activity.

The findings suggest that students engage in reading activities moderately, but not at a level that reflects strong habitual practice. Reading appears to be situational and transactional rather than consistent, often influenced by academic demands rather than intrinsic motivation. These findings are supported by the study conducted by Pandey, J. & Chandra, S. (2024) about that the majority of students (78.10%) read daily for school work purposes and only 21.17% of the respondents read every day fulfil their personal interest in reading.

This clearly stipulate a need to develop certain stimulant activities to uplift students' desire to read even without prerequisites. Through this, the establishment of an effective, independent and proficient readers is feasible.

Table 4B. *Survey results on the Reading habits of the respondents in terms of Types of Reading Materials*

Types of Reading Materials																
I read printed books, such as textbooks, novels, and magazines.	22	14.86%	45	30.41%	64	43.24%	15	10.14%	2	1.35	148	100%	0.61	3.47	S	
I read e-books or digital materials on my phone and computer.	22	14.86%	46	31.08%	69	46.62%	11	7.43%	0	0	148	100%	0.62	3.53	S	
I read online articles, blogs, and informational websites.	17	11.49%	49	33.11%	67	45.27%	14	9.46%	1	0.68	148	100%	0.61	3.45	S	
I read fictional materials (stories, comics, Wattpad, novels).	30	20.27%	47	31.76%	60	40.54%	10	6.76%	1	0.68	148	100%	0.65	3.64	O	
I read non-fiction materials (news, essays, self-help, biographies).	20	13.51%	44	29.73%	65	43.92%	18	12.16%	1	0.68	148	100%	0.61	3.43	S	

Types of Reading Materials

In terms of reading preferences, the results reveal that students are exposed to a variety of materials, with a general tendency toward digital and fictional content. E-books or digital materials recorded a weighted mean of 3.53 (Sometimes), indicating that students are increasingly engaging with reading through technological devices such as phones and computers.

Similarly, reading online articles, blogs, and informational websites obtained a mean of 3.45, suggesting that online sources are also moderately accessed, likely due to their convenience and accessibility. Printed books such as textbooks, novels, and magazines garnered a slightly higher mean of 3.47, reflecting that traditional materials are still utilized, though not as frequently as digital formats.

Reading non-fiction materials (e.g., news, essays, self-help, biographies) yielded a mean of 3.43, indicating moderate engagement with informational content, but showing that students may not prioritize these types of readings compared to more engaging formats.

Among all indicators, fictional materials (e.g., stories, comics, Wattpad novels) recorded the highest weighted mean of 3.64, interpreted as Often. This highlights students' strong preference for imaginative and entertainment-based reading, suggesting that they are more drawn to content that is relatable, enjoyable, and emotionally engaging.

In contrast, non-fiction materials registered the lowest weighted mean of 3.43, although it still falls within the Sometimes range. This suggests that while students do engage with informative texts, these are less preferred compared to fictional and digital content.

The findings indicate that students' reading preferences lean more toward fictional and digital materials, while traditional and informational texts are accessed less frequently, reflecting the influence of interest, accessibility, and modern reading habits.

Subsequently, Francis et al. (2020) stated that about 45.9% of students acquire new information through internet sources and only 4.9% of students gather information from book sources. This comprehensibly denote that majority of the students prefer digital materials, relatively because of its easier accessibility and productivity in usage.

Overall, the findings highlight that while students utilize multiple reading formats, they show a greater preference for digital and fiction-based materials, emphasizing the role of interest and accessibility in shaping reading behavior.

Table 4C. Survey results on the Reading habits of the respondents in terms of Time Spent on Reading

Time Spent on Reading																
I spend at least 30 minutes a day reading academic materials.	21	14.19%	48	32.43%	70	47.30%	6	4.05%	3	2.03	148	100%	0.62	3.52	S	
I allot time specifically for personal (non-academic) reading.	23	15.54%	40	27.03%	76	51.35%	7	4.73%	2	1.35	148	100%	0.62	3.50	S	
I spend longer hours reading when preparing for exams.	30	20.27%	52	35.14%	58	39.19%	7	4.73%	1	0.68	148	100%	0.65	3.69	O	
I manage my schedule to make sure I have enough time for reading.	27	18.24%	42	28.38%	70	47.30%	9	6.08%	0	0	148	100%	0.63	3.58	S	
I spend more time reading than on other leisure activities.	13	8.78%	37	25%	85	57.43%	12	8.11%	1	0.68	148	100%	0.58	3.33	S	
																3.48 S

Time Spent on Reading

The data show that students allocate a moderate amount of time for reading, with most indicators falling under “Sometimes” and only one reaching the “Often” level. Spending longer hours reading when preparing for exams recorded the highest weighted mean of 3.69 (Often), suggesting that students significantly increase their reading time primarily in response to academic demands or pressure.

Other indicators reflect moderate but inconsistent reading habits. Spending at least 30 minutes a day reading academic materials obtained a mean of 3.52, while managing schedules to ensure time for reading yielded a slightly higher mean of 3.58. Both are interpreted as Sometimes, indicating that although students make efforts to incorporate reading into their routine, it is not practiced consistently.

Allocating time specifically for personal (non-academic) reading garnered a mean of 3.50, also within the Sometimes range, which shows that leisure reading exists but is not strongly prioritized among students.

In contrast, spending more time reading than on other leisure activities registered the lowest weighted mean of 3.33, indicating that reading often takes a secondary role compared to other forms of entertainment. This suggests that students may prefer activities such as social media, gaming, or other non-reading pursuits during their free time.

The findings imply that students’ reading time is largely situational—intensifying during academic requirements such as exams, but remaining moderate and inconsistent in daily and leisure contexts. This pattern reflects that reading is often viewed as a task-driven activity rather than a sustained personal habit, highlighting a need to strengthen students’ motivation for regular and self-initiated reading.

Locher, F., and Pfof, M. (2020) argues that cumulative differences in reading are caused by differences in reading habits, especially the time individuals spend reading. Extracurricular and self-initiated reading fosters the development of reading skills. In turn, reading skills positively affect reading motivation and time spent reading or reading volume, both of which foster the development of reading skills.

Overall, the findings imply that students’ reading time is largely driven by necessity rather than habit, with increased engagement occurring mainly during exam preparation. This indicates a need to strengthen time management and promote consistent reading routines among students.

English Writing Skills

In the table below, the result is shown on the survey conducted with regards to the English Writing Skills of the Grade 11 Senior Highschool students of Colegio de Sta. Rita de San Carlos, Inc.

Table 5. Survey results on the English writing skills of the respondents

Hypothetical Range	F	%	WX	I
13-15 (5)	17	11.49 %		
10-12 (4)	11	7.43 %		
7-9 (3)	33	22.30 %		
4-6 (2)	76	51.35 %	2.64	SATISFACTORY
0-3 (1)	11	7.43 %		
TOTAL GWX	148	100%		

Table 6. Specific mean score of the respondents based on the three (3) indicators (Grammar, Vocabulary, Sentence Structure)

Indicators	Mean Score
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Grammar	2.9
Vocabulary	2.4
Sentence Structure	1.4

This section presents the discussion of the findings on the English writing skills of Grade 11 Senior High School students based on three key indicators: grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure. The overall result revealed a weighted mean of 2.64, interpreted as satisfactory, indicating that students possess a moderate level of writing proficiency but still require

improvement in specific areas. Writing, as a complex skill, involves the integration of grammatical knowledge, lexical competence, and syntactic organization. Recent studies emphasize that these components significantly influence the quality of students' written outputs and overall communicative competence.

The results in grammar, reflected in a mean score of 2.9, indicate that students have a fairly satisfactory to satisfactory level of grammatical competence. This suggests that learners can identify correct grammatical structures, such as subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, conditional clauses, and punctuation, as shown in the test items. However, their performance also implies occasional difficulties in applying these rules consistently in more complex contexts.

This finding aligns with the study of Marjokorpi (2023), which revealed that grammatical understanding is a strong predictor of writing quality, influencing coherence, syntax, and stylistic accuracy. Similarly, Musa (2021) found that inadequate grammar mastery leads to errors in writing, affecting clarity and correctness, particularly among secondary-level learners. Furthermore, Prihatini and Pangesti (2023) emphasized that students often struggle with writing due to insufficient grammar mastery, which limits their ability to construct meaningful and accurate sentences.

The moderate performance in grammar indicates that while students are familiar with basic grammatical rules, they may lack deeper metalinguistic awareness necessary for advanced writing. This suggests the need for contextualized grammar instruction that integrates grammar with actual writing tasks rather than isolated drills.

The vocabulary component obtained a mean score of 2.4, interpreted as fairly satisfactory, indicating that students have a limited but functional vocabulary range. The results suggest that students can recognize basic word meanings and select appropriate words in familiar contexts but may struggle with nuanced or advanced vocabulary usage.

This is consistent with Luthfiyati et al. (2023), who found that vocabulary mastery significantly influences writing skills, as it enables students to express ideas clearly and effectively. Additionally, Yuliawati (2021) reported that vocabulary knowledge has a direct and significant effect on students' writing performance, particularly in organizing ideas and producing meaningful texts. Supporting this, Samsidar et al. (2022) highlighted that limited vocabulary restricts students' ability to elaborate ideas, leading to weaker writing outputs.

The findings imply that students' vocabulary level may hinder their ability to communicate more complex thoughts in writing. A restricted vocabulary often results in repetitive word usage and lack of precision. Therefore, enriching students' lexical knowledge through reading exposure and contextual vocabulary instruction is essential to improve their writing proficiency.

The lowest mean score was recorded in sentence structure (1.4), interpreted as needs improvement, indicating that students experience significant difficulty in constructing grammatically and syntactically correct sentences. This includes challenges in forming compound and complex sentences, maintaining parallel structure, and correctly using clauses and the subjunctive mood.

This result is supported by Christina (2021), who found that sentence structure mastery has a significant correlation with writing skills, and weak syntactic ability leads to poorly organized and less coherent texts. Moreover, Dizon and Villanueva (2022) emphasized that mastery of sentence construction is essential in developing writing competence, as it directly affects clarity and organization. Recent research by Jaya et al. (2025) also demonstrated that improving syntactic complexity through sentence combining enhances both grammatical accuracy and writing fluency.

The low performance in this area suggests that students may rely heavily on simple sentence patterns and struggle to express complex relationships between ideas. This limitation significantly affects the overall quality of their writing, making it less cohesive and sophisticated. Instructional interventions focusing on sentence construction and syntactic variety are therefore highly recommended.

Overall, the findings indicate that students possess a satisfactory level of English writing skills, with grammar as their strongest area, followed by vocabulary, and sentence structure as the weakest. The results highlight that while students demonstrate basic competence in writing, they still face challenges in achieving higher-level proficiency, particularly in constructing complex sentences and expanding vocabulary.

The study confirms that grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure are interrelated components that collectively influence writing performance. Consistent with existing literature, deficiencies in any of these areas can significantly affect students' ability to produce coherent and effective written texts. Therefore, there is a need for targeted instructional strategies that integrate these components, such as contextualized grammar teaching, vocabulary enrichment programs, and explicit instruction in sentence construction.

Table 7. *Relationship between Reading Habits and English Writing Skills*

n = 148						
Variables	r	I	P-value	Decision	Remark	
Reading habits and English Writing Skills	0.118	Very low correlation	0.850	Accept Null Hypothesis	Not significant	
0.05 level of significance				df = n-1		

The correlation analysis as presented in the table revealed that there is no significant correlation between reading habits and English writing skills of the students. Based on the result, the probability value of 0.850 with the Pearson r value of 0.118, there is a positive correlation of these two variables, although the correlation is weak in nature, but it was still positive. This implies that as reading habits decrease, the English writing skills decrease.

Summary of Findings

This study assessed the reading habits and English writing skills of Grade 11 Senior High School students, as well as the relationship between these two variables.

In terms of reading habits, the findings revealed that students generally exhibit a moderate level, with an overall mean interpreted as "Sometimes." Specifically, students engage in reading activities occasionally rather than consistently. Their reading frequency is not strongly habitual and is often influenced by academic requirements. In terms of materials, students showed a greater preference for digital and fictional texts, while printed and non-fiction materials were read less frequently. Regarding time spent on reading, students allocate time moderately, with increased reading primarily occurring during exam preparation. Overall, reading is more situational than habitual, indicating a need to strengthen consistent reading practices.

For English writing skills, the results showed an overall level of "Satisfactory" (mean = 2.64). Among the three indicators, grammar emerged as the strongest area with a fairly satisfactory level, followed by vocabulary, which was also fairly satisfactory but limited. Sentence structure was identified as the weakest area, falling under "Needs Improvement," indicating significant difficulty in constructing clear and complex sentences. These findings suggest that while students possess basic writing competence, they struggle with higher-level writing skills.

In terms of the relationship between reading habits and English writing skills, the findings revealed a very low positive correlation ($r = 0.118$) with a p -value of 0.850, indicating that the relationship is not statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that although a slight positive relationship exists, reading habits do not significantly influence students' writing skills in this study.

Overall, the findings indicate that students demonstrate moderate reading habits and satisfactory writing skills, but these two variables do not have a significant relationship.

Intervention

The proposed Reading-to-Writing Enhancement Program is designed to address the moderate level of reading habits and the satisfactory level of English writing skills among Grade 11 students. Although the findings of the study revealed no significant relationship between reading habits and writing skills, it remains essential to strengthen these competencies independently, as both contribute significantly to students' academic performance and communicative competence. Writing is a multidimensional skill that involves grammar, vocabulary, and sentence structure, all of which require systematic and sustained instructional support (Kim et al., 2021).

The program will begin with the implementation of scheduled and supervised reading sessions, where students will engage with a variety of texts such as short stories, essays, academic materials, and informational articles. Exposure to diverse reading materials allows students to internalize language patterns, expand vocabulary, and develop awareness of different writing styles. Research shows that grammar and vocabulary mastery significantly influence writing performance, as these elements help learners produce coherent and meaningful texts (Luthfiyati et al., 2023).

To complement this, guided writing workshops will be conducted regularly, focusing on improving grammar, vocabulary usage, sentence structure, and coherence. These workshops will adopt a process-oriented and competence-based approach, including modeling, guided practice, and collaborative activities such as peer editing. Effective writing instruction has been shown to significantly improve writing quality, fluency, and organization when learners are given structured and explicit guidance (Kim et al., 2021; Msuya & Abdala, 2025).

Moreover, the program will incorporate reading response activities, such as reflections, summaries, reaction papers, and short essays. These activities will enable students to develop higher-order thinking skills, including analysis and evaluation, which are essential for meaningful writing. Recent studies emphasize that writing development goes beyond grammar and vocabulary and requires the integration of critical thinking to construct and communicate ideas effectively (Zahra & Wijayatiningsih, 2024).

In addition, vocabulary enrichment activities will be integrated into the program through vocabulary journals, contextual learning, and interactive exercises. Vocabulary knowledge plays a crucial role in writing, as limited lexical resources often hinder students' ability to express ideas clearly and effectively (Anistasya, 2022).

Furthermore, the program will emphasize sentence structure development, particularly in constructing complex and coherent sentences. Studies have shown that difficulties in sentence construction and syntactic organization significantly affect writing clarity and overall performance, highlighting the need for explicit instruction in sentence formation (Matusalem et al., 2025; Cabilan et al., 2026).

Additionally, the program will promote a supportive and motivating literacy environment through school-wide reading campaigns, classroom-based challenges, and interactive literacy activities. Teachers will play a central role in facilitating instruction, monitoring progress, and providing feedback, which has been found to enhance students' writing self-efficacy and engagement (Yang, 2025).

Through consistent implementation, the Reading-to-Writing Enhancement Program is expected to gradually improve students' reading engagement and writing competence. While reading habits and writing skills may not show a direct statistical relationship in this study, strengthening these areas can still lead to meaningful improvements in students' overall language proficiency, confidence, and academic performance.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that Grade 11 Senior High School students of Colegio de Santa Rita de San Carlos Incorporated demonstrate moderate reading habits and a satisfactory level of English writing skills, indicating that students possess basic literacy abilities but still need further development to achieve higher proficiency.

The results show that students engage in reading, but not consistently enough for it to become a strong habit. Reading is often done in response to academic tasks rather than personal interest, suggesting that students are not yet fully motivated to read independently. Their preference for digital and fictional materials reflects the influence of accessibility and engagement, which supports the findings of Francis et al. (2020) that students tend to rely more on digital sources. Similarly, Pandey and Chandra (2024) emphasized that students are more inclined to read for school-related purposes than for leisure. This pattern indicates that while students are exposed to reading, it is not sustained in a way that strongly supports continuous literacy development. As noted by Locher and Pfof (2020), consistent and extended reading engagement is essential in strengthening reading skills, which further highlights the need to improve students' reading routines.

In terms of writing, students demonstrate basic competence, particularly in grammar and vocabulary, but encounter difficulties in sentence structure, which affects the clarity and organization of their written work. This suggests that students can express ideas at a simple level but struggle to construct more complex and coherent sentences. This finding is supported by Christina (2021) and Dizon and Villanueva (2022), who emphasized that mastery of sentence structure is crucial in producing clear and effective writing. In addition, Luthfiyati et al. (2023) pointed out that limited vocabulary can restrict students' ability to express ideas more precisely, further affecting writing quality. These results affirm that writing is a complex skill that requires the integration of multiple components, including grammar, vocabulary, and sentence construction (Irmawati et al., 2024).

Furthermore, the study revealed that reading habits and writing skills do not have a significant relationship in this context. This suggests that improving reading alone may not automatically lead to better writing performance. Instead, writing skills are influenced by various factors such as instruction, practice, and language exposure. This finding implies that both reading and writing should be developed independently while still being supported together in the learning process.

In general, the study highlights the need for more consistent reading engagement and focused writing instruction. Encouraging students to develop regular reading habits and providing targeted support in areas such as sentence structure and vocabulary can help improve their overall language proficiency. Strengthening these skills is essential not only for academic success but also for effective communication.

Recommendation

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to further enhance the reading habits and English writing skills of students, as well as to guide future research:

Primarily, it is recommended that schools and teachers implement structured reading programs that encourage consistent and independent reading among students. Since the findings revealed that reading is often situational rather than habitual, activities such as scheduled reading time, exposure to diverse reading materials, and reading motivation programs may help develop sustained reading engagement. Teachers may also integrate both digital and print resources to align with students' interests while gradually promoting academic and non-fiction reading.

Second, there is a need to strengthen writing instruction, particularly in the area of sentence structure, which was identified as the weakest component. Educators are encouraged to provide more guided writing activities, including sentence construction exercises, paragraph development tasks, and writing workshops that emphasize coherence and organization. Vocabulary enrichment activities and contextualized grammar instruction should also be incorporated to support overall writing development.

Third, future researchers are encouraged to conduct a more substantial and comprehensive study involving a wider and larger number of respondents to improve the generalizability of the findings. Expanding the sample size across different schools or regions may provide a broader perspective on students' reading habits and writing skills.

Additionally, it is recommended that future studies utilize a more extensive questionnaire with a greater number of items and additional indicators. For reading habits, researchers may include factors such as reading motivation, reading environment, and access to materials. For writing skills, additional indicators such as organization, coherence, and critical thinking may be explored to provide a more in-depth assessment.

Subsequently, future researchers may consider employing mixed-method approaches, incorporating qualitative data such as interviews or open-ended responses to gain deeper insights into students' experiences, challenges, and attitudes toward reading and writing. This can provide a more holistic understanding beyond quantitative results.

For future studies, researchers may explore other variables that could influence writing skills, such as teaching strategies, language exposure, use of technology, and students' learning motivation. Investigating these factors may help explain the lack of significant relationship found in this study and contribute to the development of more effective instructional interventions. These recommendations aim to support the continuous improvement of students' literacy skills and to provide direction for more comprehensive and meaningful future research.

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